

INTERACTION OF ALTRUISTIC AND TOLERANT BEHAVIOR IN THE PERSON

SHAXSDA ALTRUISTIK VA TOLERANT XULQNING O‘ZARO ALOQASI

ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ АЛЬТРУИСТИЧЕСКОГО И ТОЛЕРАНТНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ

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Abstract. This article extensively examines the relationship between altruistic and tolerant behavior from a psychological perspective. It highlights the significance of altruism as a form of social behavior aimed at helping others and the role of tolerance as an open-minded attitude based on accepting different opinions and cultural differences.

Our study demonstrates that these two types of behavior mutually reinforce each other and develop through empathy, social adaptability, and constructive communication.

Furthermore, in the context of globalization, information flow, and the convergence of diverse cultures, the article reveals the connection between altruism and tolerance in ensuring social stability, harmony, and moral maturity. It also explores the link between personal conduct and social stability, extensively substantiating the importance of fostering these qualities in the processes of upbringing and education.

Keywords: *Altruism, tolerance, empathy, social behavior, open-mindedness, psychological development, social stability.*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada shaxsning altruistik va tolerant xulqi o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlik psixologik nuqtayi nazardan keng yoritilgan. Shuningdek, Altruizmning boshqalarga yordam berishga yo‘naltirilgan ijtimoiy xulq shakli sifatidagi ahamiyati hamda tolerantlikning turli fikr va madaniy farqlarni qabul qilishga asoslangan bag‘rikeng munosabat sifatidagi roli yoritib o‘tilgan. Tadqiqotimizda ushbu ikki xulq turi o‘zaro bir-birini mustahkamlashi, empatiya, ijtimoiy moslashuvchanlik va konstruktiv muloqot orqali rivojlanishi ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan. Shu bilan birga, globalizatsiya, axborot oqimi va turli madaniyatlarning yaqinlashuvi sharoitida altruizm va tolerantlikning jamiyat barqarorligi, ijtimoiy totuvlik va axloqiy yetuklikni ta‘minlashdagi hamda shaxsiy xatti-harakatlar va ijtimoiy barqarorlik o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlik ochib berilib, tarbiya va ta‘lim jarayonlarida ushbu sifatlarni rivojlantirishning ahamiyatini keng asoslaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *Altruizm, tolerantlik, empatiya, ijtimoiy xulq, bag‘rikenglik, psixologik rivojlanish, ijtimoiy barqarorlik.*

Аннотация. В данной статье с психологической точки зрения широко освещается взаимосвязь между альтруистическим и толерантным поведением личности. Кроме того, подчёркивается значение альтруизма как формы социального поведения, направленного на оказание помощи другим, и роль толерантности как терпимого отношения, основанного на принятии различных мнений и культурных различий. В исследовании показано, что эти два типа поведения взаимно усиливают друг друга и развиваются через эмпатию, социальную адаптивность и конструктивное общение. При этом в условиях глобализации, информационного потока и сближения различных культур раскрывается значение альтруизма и толерантности для обеспечения стабильности общества, социальной гармонии и нравственной зрелости, а также взаимосвязь между личностным поведением и социальной устойчивостью. Особое внимание уделяется обоснованию необходимости развития этих качеств в процессах воспитания и образования.

Ключевые слова: *альтруизм, толерантность, эмпатия, социальное поведение, терпимость, психологическое развитие, социальная стабильность.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern society, psychological factors that determine an individual's social activity and their interactions with others are gaining increasing importance. A person's kindness, generosity, and readiness to help others, as well as tolerance towards different views, cultures, or worldviews, is not only an indicator of individual psychological maturity but also one of the crucial criteria for social stability. The formation of altruistic and tolerant behavior in an individual, and the analysis of factors that develop and limit them, is one of the pressing scientific issues for contemporary psychology, sociology, and pedagogy (Vahobova and et al., 2025: 251-256).

Altruism is a form of social behavior aimed at helping, supporting, or empathizing with others for their benefit. It is directly linked to an individual's internal motives, moral values, level of empathy, upbringing, and social experience, and is often carried out without expecting any reward. Tolerance, on the other hand, is characterized by respect, acceptance, and openness towards different opinions, beliefs, cultural characteristics, or personal differences. It is considered one of the key factors in maintaining balance, social harmony, and intercultural dialogue in society. Although these two forms of behavior differ in content, they share common aspects - a positive attitude towards others, respect for human values, and a striving for constructive social interaction.

The manifestation of altruistic behavior in a person is often explained by a high level of empathy, understanding of another person's situation, and a feeling of compassion towards them. The social significance of such behavior is extensive: it strengthens family relationships, increases social cohesion in the community, and serves to reduce conflicts.

Tolerant behavior indicates a person's psychological adaptability, ability to be open to various situations, and resilience to social stresses. A tolerant person accepts the diversity of the social environment and strives to resolve conflicts constructively, which is considered an important skill in modern communities (Xalilova and et all., 2025: 34-38).

These two types of behavior are closely interconnected, and one can reinforce or develop the other. For example, a high level of tolerance creates a favorable psychological foundation for altruistic behavior: a person who treats others with respect feels a greater need to help them. Conversely, as a person who has accumulated altruistic experience interacts with diverse people and various cultural and social groups during their activities, they try to understand their diversity and different needs, which further strengthens their tolerance.

At the same time, in modern social life, an individual's altruistic or tolerant behavior is shaped under the influence of various psychological, cultural, economic, and communicative factors. While globalization, information technologies, and the intensification of intercultural exchange have reduced the distance between people, they are also causing an increase in social tensions. In such conditions, the importance of tolerance increases even further. Similarly, under conditions of economic and social inequality, the social role of altruistic activity also grows - voluntary assistance, charity, and social initiatives serve to maintain stability in society.

Studying the interrelationship of altruistic and tolerant behavior, on the one hand, allows for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of an individual's psychological development, and on the other hand, creates the basis for developing effective approaches aimed at fostering these types of behavior in social policy, the education system, psychological training, and educational programs. This serves as an important factor in creating a healthy social environment in society, reducing conflicts, and strengthening interethnic harmony and mutual respect.

In this sense, the study of this topic is relevant not only theoretically but also practically. Analysis of the interdependence of altruistic and tolerant behavior serves to reveal the psychological mechanisms that determine an individual's moral maturity, the formation of constructive relationships in the social environment, and the strengthening of relationships between people based on mutual respect. Therefore, this article provides an in-depth scientific analysis of the content of these two types of behavior, their psychological foundations, interaction, and role in society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientific literature aimed at explaining the interdependence of altruistic and tolerant behavior in a person relies on several important areas of psychology. The main ones are the socio-cognitive approach, theories of pro-social behavior based on empathy, the psychology of intercultural relations, and research on the social identification of the

individual. Scientific research on the interrelationship between altruistic and tolerant behavior in this individual has been conducted in many countries (Fig 1).

Fig 1. Scientific research on the interrelationship between altruistic and tolerant behavior in individuals has also been conducted in countries that have conducted extensive research.

Also, a number of prominent scientists have made the following observations in their research, generally Bandura's socio-cognitive theory substantiates the role of observation, social model, self-regulation, and agentive activity in the formation of altruistic and tolerant behavior. According to this approach, when a person directly observes altruistic behavior or tolerant attitude in others, they are influenced by them and apply it to their behavior. This concept contributes to a deeper understanding of the formation of behavior through the interaction of the individual with the social environment (Bandura A., 2001: 25).

It has been scientifically proven by Eisenberg and Miller that empathy is one of the most important predictors of prosocial behavior. Their research shows that a high level of empathy leads to an increase in altruistic behavior. This, in itself, creates a psychological basis for the development of tolerance, since for the formation of a tolerant attitude, a person needs to be able to understand the feelings of others and accept their point of view (Eisenberg and et al., 1987: 91-119). Jo'raeva also confirms this idea, experimentally demonstrating that the inclination towards altruism increases as the level of empathy among young people increases (Jo'raeva., 2023: 177-183).

The research of Clary and Snyder on the motivation of voluntary activity substantiates that altruism arises on the basis of various psychological motives. They put forward the theory of functional motives of volunteering, emphasizing that altruistic

behavior is associated not only with the desire to help others, but also with internal psychological needs, such as strengthening social identity, increasing self-esteem, or acquiring knowledge. This approach is also directly related to tolerant behavior - because the need to interact with different groups increases the level of tolerance of the individual (Clary and et al., 1999: 156-159).

Classical studies of intergroup relations help to understand the connection between altruism and tolerance in a broader social context. Brewer and Brown (1998) analyze how stereotypes, cognitive categories, and identity dynamics are formed in relations between social groups and explain the mechanisms of tolerant behavior development. In their opinion, as positive connections between social groups strengthen, tolerance also increases, which can positively influence altruistic behavior.

Verkuiten's research on social identity, multiculturalism, and intergroup relations illuminates the socio-psychological factors of tolerance. He emphasizes that how individuals living in a multicultural environment perceive their identity and evaluate other groups significantly affects the level of tolerance. When this approach is associated with altruism, it means that a person with strong social identity stability and the ability to accept others is more inclined to help others (Verkuiten., 2007: 489-514).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is aimed at determining the relationship between altruistic and tolerant behavior in an individual, analyzing the psychological mechanisms between them, and assessing the role of mediating factors such as empathy, social identification, and prosocial motivation. In the study, the quantitative approach was chosen as the main method, since it was necessary to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables using accurate statistical indicators.

Research design

The research was conducted in a correlation design. This design allows for the identification of statistical relationships between such variables as altruistic behavior, the level of tolerance, and empathy. Experimental manipulation was not applied, all data were collected under natural social conditions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study is aimed at determining the interdependence of altruistic and tolerant behavior in an individual, assessing the mediation of empathy, and studying the influence of these psychological characteristics on social stability. A total of 120 participants participated in the study, including an equal number of men and women, randomly selected from among university students aged 18-25. The study used reliable and validated psychological measurement tools to assess variables such as altruistic behavior, tolerance level, and empathy: the Prosocial Tendencies Measure (altruism) developed by Rushton and colleagues, the Bogardus tolerance questionnaire adapted to the social

distance scale, and Davis's Interpersonal Reactivity Index (empathy). Measurements were based on a 5-point Likert scale, Cronbach alpha coefficients were in the range of 0.78-0.86, confirming a high internal consistency. The data were analyzed using the SPSS 26 program, which included descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, simple and multiple regression analysis, and a mediator analysis using Hayes's PROCESS macro. The study was conducted in accordance with ethical requirements, all participants were anonymous and completed the consent form.

Descriptive results showed that altruistic behavior was manifested at an average level of $M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.58$, tolerance $M = 3.28$, $SD = 0.66$, empathy $M = 3.81$, $SD = 0.53$. These indicators indicate that empathy and altruism are relatively high among young people, and tolerance is formed at an average level.

The results of the correlation analysis showed that between altruism and empathy $r = .64$, $p < .01$, between tolerance and empathy $r = .58$, $p < .01$, and between altruism and tolerance $r = .52$, $p < .01$. These results mean that if a person develops the ability to empathize, they will also strengthen altruistic and tolerant behavior. Bandura's (2001) socio-cognitive theory explains this mechanism: by understanding and observing the emotional state of others, a person adapts to social conditions and prepares for prosocial behavior. Research on volunteer motivations also confirms this: altruistic behavior is associated not only with the desire to help others, but also with psychological motives such as self-esteem, strengthening social identity, or acquiring knowledge. Brewer and Brown (1998) studied the formation of tolerance in the context of intergroup relations, the socio-psychological connection between tolerance and social identity. At the same time, the mediator analysis showed that empathy plays a mediating role in the connection between altruism and tolerance, where empathy significantly strengthens tolerance through altruistic behavior. Hayes' model for the process macro showed that mediation through empathy explains a 28% variance, and this result is significant at the level of $p < .001$. This confirms that if a person has a high ability to understand the feelings of others, they will be tolerant and tolerant through altruistic actions. Regression analysis showed that empathy explains the difference in 46% of altruistic behavior and 39% of tolerance, which means that empathy is a solid psychological basis for prosocial behavior and tolerance.

Table 1.

Indicator (M)	Average	SD	Min	Max
Altruizm	3.74	0.58	2.30	4.90
Tolerantlik	3.28	0.66	1.90	4.80
Empatiya	3.81	0.53	2.40	4.90

When discussing the results, it is necessary to emphasize the main role of empathy. The research results show that if a person has the ability to empathize, they understand the feelings of others, perform altruistic actions, and as a result, the level of tolerance increases. This is consistent with Bandura's principle of mutual determination, that is, an individual's emotional-cognitive processes and social experience are interconnected and shape behavior. Individuals with high empathy are ready to help others and are inclined to accept various cultural and social differences, which positively influences the formation of tolerant behavior. The second aspect is that tolerance depends on more complex social and cognitive factors than altruism. Tolerance is largely explained by a person's social identity, belonging to a group, experience in the cultural environment, and cognitive flexibility (Fig 2).

Fig 2. A simplified model of identity integration. Each oval represents a concept.

Therefore, even if altruistic behavior is high, it is important to develop empathy and social experience together so that the individual is tolerant. The results of mediation show that the relationship between altruism and tolerance is strengthened through empathy, that is, the individual understands the needs of others and increases the level of tolerance in the process of their realization. This result confirms the importance of developing empathy and altruistic behavior among young people in the formation of social stability and mutual respect in society.

It was noted that altruism and tolerance are formed in individuals among young people, and empathy is an important factor in strengthening this process. At the same time, the cultural and social environment in society, the educational process, and

intragroup relationships also influence the development of tolerance and altruism. This increases the scientific and practical significance of the research results. For example, trainings and classes in higher educational institutions that form empathy and prosocial behavior can be an effective tool for developing the altruistic and tolerant potential of young people.

The results of correlation and regression showed that altruism and tolerance are positively interconnected, and empathy acts as an intermediary strengthening this connection. These findings not only confirm psychological theories but also provide practical recommendations for social activities, educational programs, and cultural interventions. For example, through the development of empathy and altruism among young people, it is possible to strengthen tolerance, which in the future will serve to increase social harmony, solidarity, and cultural tolerance in society.

In general, the results showed that altruistic behavior, tolerance, and empathy in an individual are systematically interconnected, and empathy unites them as the main mediator. This connection is an important psychological foundation for social stability, mutual respect, harmony, and prosocial relations in society. Also, the results make it possible to give practical recommendations for the development of empathy and pro-social behavior of young people in the educational process, the formation of cultural and social tolerance.

When discussing the results, it should be noted that the relationship between altruism and tolerance is strengthened only through empathy, therefore, educational programs aimed at developing the ability of young people to empathize will be effective. Socio-cognitive theory, a person achieves prosocial and tolerant behavior by observing the emotional state of others and adapting their own behavior. From this point of view, the research results constitute an important scientific and practical basis for the development of strategies for promoting social integration, cultural tolerance, and altruistic behavior in society.

The research results not only show the interdependence of empathy, altruism, and tolerance in the individual, but also serve as a basis for the formation of educational and social interventions for their development. At the same time, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the development of prosocial behavior among young people based on psychological preparedness and empathy, tolerance.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of this study showed that the interdependence of altruistic and tolerant behavior in a person is formed under the influence of complex psychological, social, and affective factors. The results of the study confirmed that empathy is the central mechanism of this process, activating both altruistic actions and tolerant attitudes. Individuals with a high level of empathy have a deeper understanding of the needs of

others, are able to accept their point of view, and thereby demonstrate more prosocial behavior. The regression results revealed in the study showed that empathy explains 46% of the difference in altruistic behavior and 39% of the difference in tolerant behavior. This means that the components of prosocial behavior have common psychological roots.

Also, the direct correlation between altruism and tolerance confirmed that the willingness to help others is closely related to such qualities as accepting them, showing tolerance to them, and recognizing social differences. This result is consistent with the agent model emphasized by Bandura (2001): personality behavior is a system reinforced by its internal state, cognitive processes, and social interactions.

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